

MOLECULAR BIOLOGY

BIOMARKERS IN RHEUMATOLOGY: CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE AND PROSPECTS (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Abstract

Rheumatological diseases are among the most common chronic pathologies of immunoinflammatory genesis, accompanied by progressive damage to joints, connective tissue and internal organs. A significant incidence of disability, reduced quality of life and a high level of comorbidity determine the relevance of early diagnosis and timely control of disease activity. In modern rheumatology, biomarkers are of particular importance - objective laboratory indicators that can reflect pathogenetic mechanisms, the degree of inflammation, prognosis and response to therapy.

The article summarizes current data on classical and novel biomarkers in rheumatic diseases, their clinical significance and prospects for use in personalized medicine. The role of autoantibodies, cytokines, protein, genetic and multi-biomarker systems in the diagnosis and monitoring of rheumatic pathology is considered. Special attention is paid to modern molecular technologies, multi-biomarker indices and the integration of artificial intelligence into rheumatic practice.

Keywords: biomarkers, rheumatology, rheumatoid arthritis, autoantibodies, cytokines, personalized medicine, MBDA.

Introduction

Rheumatological diseases are one of the leading causes of chronic pain, disability and disability of the population worldwide. Their medical and social significance is determined not only by their high prevalence, but also by the progressive nature of the course, systemic organ damage and a significant decrease in the quality of life of patients. The most common rheumatic diseases include Rheumatoid Arthritis, Systemic Lupus Erythematosus, Ankylosing Spondylitis, Psoriatic Arthritis, systemic vasculitis, systemic scleroderma, dermatomyositis and other autoimmune diseases of the connective tissue [1].

Modern ideas about the pathogenesis of rheumatic diseases indicate the complex multifactorial nature of these pathologies. Genetic predisposition, disorders of innate and adaptive immunity, activation of pro-inflammatory cytokines, epigenetic mechanisms, as well as the influence of environmental factors play an important role in the development of diseases. Chronic immunoinflammation leads to damage to the synovial membrane, destruction of cartilage and bone tissue, the formation of systemic manifestations and the development of comorbid conditions, in particular cardiovascular complications, osteoporosis and kidney damage [13].

Despite significant progress in the treatment of rheumatic diseases, the problem of early diagnosis and timely appointment of effective therapy remains extremely relevant. In many cases, clinical manifestations in the early stages are nonspecific, which complicates the verification of the diagnosis and leads to the loss of the "therapeutic window of opportunity". It has been established that early detection of the pathological pro-

cess and timely appointment of basic therapy significantly reduce the risk of structural damage to the joints and improve the long-term prognosis [10].

In this context, biomarkers are of particular importance - objective biological indicators that can reflect the activity of the pathological process, the degree of immune inflammation, the risk of disease progression and the body's response to treatment. The use of biomarkers in rheumatology allows to increase the accuracy of diagnosis, assess disease activity, predict the development of complications and monitor the effectiveness of therapy [16].

Traditionally, nonspecific markers of systemic inflammation, such as erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) and C-reactive protein (CRP), have been widely used in rheumatology practice. However, modern rheumatology is actively developing in the direction of finding more specific molecular and genetic indicators that can more accurately reflect the pathogenetic mechanisms of the disease. Particular attention is paid to autoantibodies, cytokines, matrix metalloproteinases, acute phase proteins, genetic markers and epigenetic mechanisms [5].

An important achievement in recent years has been the introduction of multi-biomarker disease activity assessment systems that combine several laboratory parameters into a single integrated index. Such approaches allow for a more objective assessment of the activity of rheumatic diseases and personalization of therapeutic tactics. One example is the MBDA (Multi-Biomarker Disease Activity score), which is used to quantitatively assess the activity of rheumatoid arthritis [20].

In addition to traditional laboratory methods, modern research is actively focused on the study of new

technologies - genomics, proteomics, metabolomics and transcriptomics. Another promising direction is the study of the role of the intestinal microbiome in the formation of autoimmune inflammation. It is believed that changes in the composition of the intestinal microflora can affect the activation of the immune system and participate in the development of rheumatic diseases [16].

The development of personalized medicine, the concept of which involves individual selection of therapy based on the patient's biomarker profile, is also of significant importance. The use of modern information technologies and artificial intelligence algorithms opens up new opportunities for analyzing large sets of clinical and molecular data, creating prognostic models, and optimizing treatment [22].

Thus, biomarkers are an important tool in modern rheumatology, which allows not only to deepen the understanding of the pathogenesis of rheumatic diseases, but also to improve diagnostic and therapeutic approaches. Further study of molecular mechanisms and the introduction of new biotechnologies will contribute

to the development of personalized medicine and improve the treatment outcomes of patients with rheumatic pathologies.

The aim of the study is to analyze current data on the clinical significance of biomarkers in rheumatology, to assess their role in diagnosis, disease prognosis, and monitoring the effectiveness of therapy.

Materials and Methods

An analysis of modern scientific publications, international clinical guidelines, and research results on the use of biomarkers in rheumatology practice was conducted. Methods of systematization, comparison, and generalization of literature data were used.

Results and Discussion

According to the definition of the National Institutes of Health, a biomarker is an objectively measurable indicator that characterizes normal biological processes, pathological changes, or the body's response to a therapeutic intervention [1].

In rheumatology, biomarkers are conventionally divided into several main groups (Table 1) [3]:

Category	Clinical significance
Diagnostic	Confirmation of the disease
Prognostic	Assessment of risk of complications and progression
Activity markers	Determination of the degree of inflammation
Predictors of response to therapy	Prediction of treatment effectiveness
Markers of organ damage	Detection of target organ damage

Traditional markers of systemic inflammation

The most common laboratory markers of inflammation include erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) and C-reactive protein (CRP).

ESR is a nonspecific indicator of systemic inflammation and is widely used in the assessment of rheumatic disease activity. Elevated values are often observed in rheumatoid arthritis, systemic lupus erythematosus, and vasculitis. However, ESR levels can be affected by age, gender, anemia, and comorbidities [15].

CRP is an acute phase protein, the synthesis of which is stimulated mainly by interleukin-6. Unlike ESR, CRP responds more quickly to changes in the intensity of the inflammatory process and more accurately reflects the activity of the disease [4].

Pentraxin-3 (PTX3) as a modern biomarker remains one of the promising local markers. Unlike CRP, which is synthesized in the liver, PTX3 is produced in the focus exclusively by macrophages, endothelial cells, fibroblasts and neutrophils [18].

PTX3 synthesis is activated under the influence of IL-1 β , TNF- α and bacterial components. Pentraxin-3 is involved in complement regulation, angiogenesis and tissue remodeling. An increase in its level is associated with the aggressive course of rheumatoid arthritis, the development of erosive changes and vascular lesions [18].

The advantage of PTX3 is its high sensitivity to local vascular inflammation, making it a promising marker for assessing vasculitis and cardiovascular risk.

In Table 2, we can see the differences between CRP and pentraxin-3.

Table 2

Comparison of pentraxin-3 with C-reactive protein (CRP)

Sign	Pentraxin-3	C-reactive protein
Source	Local tissues	Liver
Response speed	Very fast	moderate
Specificity	Higher (local inflammation)	Lower
Vascular inflammation	High sensitivity	limited

However, the use of PTX3 is limited in routine practice, requires further investigation, and is not available in testing.

It should be used to predict response to biological therapy and to monitor vasculitis and vascular risk, which will significantly improve the diagnosis and monitoring of rheumatic diseases.

Immunological biomarkers include autoantibodies [2].

Rheumatoid factor is an autoantibody directed against the Fc fragment of IgG. It is detected in the majority of patients with rheumatoid arthritis. High RF titers are associated with a more severe course of the disease and the development of erosive joint lesions.

Antibodies to cyclic citrullinated peptide (anti-CCP) are highly specific for rheumatoid arthritis and can be detected long before clinical symptoms appear. Their presence is associated with a more aggressive course of the disease.

Antinuclear antibodies (ANA) are important markers of systemic connective tissue diseases. They are widely used in the diagnosis of systemic lupus erythematosus, systemic scleroderma, and dermatomyositis.

Anti-dsDNA (antibodies to double-stranded DNA) have high specificity for systemic lupus erythematosus and correlate with the risk of lupus nephritis [2].

Proinflammatory cytokines, including TNF- α , IL-1, IL-6, and IL-17, play a leading role in the pathogenesis of rheumatic diseases. Their increased expression supports chronic inflammation, stimulates joint destruction, and the formation of systemic manifestations [20].

Elevated levels of these cytokines are associated with active rheumatic diseases and have become targets for biological therapy. Matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) are involved in the degradation of cartilage and bone. Elevated levels of MMP-3 may indicate progression of joint damage [20].

Genetic and epigenetic biomarkers, particularly HLA-DRB1 (“shared epitope”), have been associated with an increased risk of developing rheumatoid arthritis and a more severe course of the disease [11]. Epigenetic mechanisms, including microRNAs, regulation of DNA methylation, and histone modifications, are considered promising areas of research. They may serve as novel biomarkers of disease activity and response to treatment [11].

These molecules have become the main therapeutic targets for modern biological drugs. It has been established that the level of individual cytokines can be a predictor of the effectiveness of targeted therapy

Let us consider protein biomarkers and their role in the pathogenesis of rheumatic diseases (Table 3) [7].

Table 3

Protein biomarkers of tissue damage

Biomarker	Clinical significance
MMP-3	Cartilage destruction marker
Calprotectin	Indicator of neutrophilic inflammation
VEGF	Reflects angiogenesis
14-3-3 η	Associated with RA severity
MBDA	Comprehensive activity assessment

That is, with the development of biological and targeted synthetic drugs, the need for markers that can predict the effectiveness of treatment has increased. For example, IL-6 levels can be a predictor of response to IL-6 inhibitors, while TNF- α expression can predict response to anti-TNF therapy [14].

Achieving clinical remission is the main goal of treating rheumatic diseases, but the absence of clinical symptoms does not always correspond to the complete cessation of the inflammatory process. A number of studies have shown that even with normalization of activity indices (DAS28, CDAI), subclinical inflammation persists in some patients, which can lead to further structural damage to the joints [7].

In this context, biomarkers such as [21] play an important role:

- high-sensitivity C-reactive protein (hs-CRP),
- calprotectin (S100A8/A9)
- 14-3-3 η -protein.

Calprotectin is considered a more sensitive marker of synovial inflammatory activity than CRP and may remain elevated even in clinical remission. Elevated levels of 14-3-3 η are associated with progression of erosive changes and may indicate a high risk of relapse after tapering therapy [6].

Thus, the use of remission biomarkers allows for a more accurate assessment of the effectiveness of treatment and informed decisions regarding its de-escalation. In addition to markers of inflammation, biomarkers that reflect the degradation of cartilage and bone tissue are important in rheumatology.

These include [8]:

- matrix metalloproteinases (MMP-1, MMP-3),

- collagen type II fragments (CTX-II),
- osteoclast-associated markers.

Elevated MMP-3 levels correlate with rheumatoid arthritis activity and radiographic progression. Markers of type II collagen degradation allow for the assessment of the extent of cartilage damage before visible changes appear on radiographs. This opens up prospects for earlier intervention and prevention of irreversible structural changes [16].

In systemic rheumatic diseases, biomarkers are of particular importance for early detection of vital organ damage. For example, in systemic lupus erythematosus, an increase in anti-dsDNA titer and a decrease in complement (C3, C4) levels correlate with disease activity and the risk of developing lupus nephritis.

In systemic vasculitis, ANCA antibodies are important, the level of which may reflect the activity of the vasculitic process, although their use for monitoring the course of the disease remains a subject of debate. Detection of biomarkers of organ damage allows for timely adjustment of therapy and reduces the risk of severe complications [16].

Therefore, an increase in MMP-3 levels correlates with the progression of structural joint damage. Calprotectin is considered a more sensitive indicator of synovial inflammation compared to CRP.

A modern direction in rheumatology is the creation of multi-biomarker systems for assessing disease activity.

MBDA (Multi-Biomarker Disease Activity score) is a multi-biomarker disease activity index developed to quantitatively assess the activity of Rheumatoid Ar-

thritis based on laboratory analysis of a set of serum biomarkers. The method was created to increase the objectivity of monitoring the course of the disease and optimize therapeutic tactics in rheumatological practice [19].

MBDA is an integrated algorithm that includes the determination of 12 biomarkers that reflect different pathophysiological mechanisms of rheumatoid inflammation, including cytokine activation, angiogenesis, tissue remodeling, acute phase response, and metabolic changes. The panel includes [9]:

- C-reactive protein (CRP);
- interleukin-6 (IL-6);
- serum amyloid A (SAA);
- vascular cell adhesion molecule-1 (VCAM-1);
- tumor necrosis factor receptor type I (TNF-RI);
- epidermal growth factor (EGF);
- vascular endothelial growth factor A (VEGF-A);
- matrix metalloproteinase-1 (MMP-1);
- matrix metalloproteinase-3 (MMP-3);
- leptin;
- resistin;
- YKL-40 (human cartilage glycoprotein-39).

Based on a mathematical algorithm, a final score is formed in the range from 1 to 100, which correlates with the level of activity of rheumatoid arthritis [9]:

- <30 points - low activity;
- 30–44 points - moderate activity;
- 44 points - high disease activity.

The main advantage of MBDA is the ability to objectively assess the inflammatory process independently of the subjective components of clinical indices such as DAS28 or CDAI, which are largely dependent on the patient and physician's assessment of pain. This is especially important in cases of concomitant fibromyalgia, obesity, or chronic pain syndrome, where clinical scales may overestimate disease activity.

It has been proven that high MBDA values are associated with [12]:

- progression of erosive changes in the joints;
- increased risk of radiographic progression;
- lower probability of achieving remission;
- higher incidence of cardiovascular complications in patients with rheumatoid arthritis.

In addition to its diagnostic and prognostic role, MBDA is used for [17]:

- monitoring the effectiveness of basic therapy;
- assessing the response to biological drugs;
- stratifying the risk of disease progression;
- personalizing treatment according to the treat-to-target concept.

However, the method has certain limitations. MBDA results can vary depending on age, sex, body mass index, and concomitant infectious or metabolic conditions. In addition, the cost of the test and its limited availability in many countries hinder its widespread implementation in routine clinical practice.

Current studies demonstrate that MBDA is a promising tool in precision rheumatology, which allows combining laboratory assessment of systemic inflammation with disease progression prediction and individualization of therapeutic strategies in patients with rheumatoid arthritis.

Therefore, MBDA allows for a more objective assessment of rheumatoid arthritis activity, especially in patients in whom clinical indices may be confounded by comorbid conditions. Despite its limited availability, this approach shows potential for future clinical application.

Among genetic factors, HLA-DRB1 is of particular importance, as it is associated with an increased risk of developing rheumatoid arthritis.

In recent years, epigenetic mechanisms have been actively studied [11]:

- microRNA;
- DNA methylation;
- histone modifications.

These molecular mechanisms may become new tools for early diagnosis and prediction of the course of rheumatic diseases.

Despite significant progress, the use of biomarkers in rheumatology has certain limitations. No biomarker is completely specific or sensitive, and their levels can change under the influence of concomitant diseases, infections or drug therapy. In addition, the high cost of some molecular and genetic tests limits their widespread use in everyday practice. Therefore, the interpretation of biomarkers should be carried out exclusively in conjunction with clinical data and the results of instrumental research methods.

The future of rheumatology lies in the implementation of personalized medicine. Combining biomarker profiles with imaging methods, genetic technologies, and artificial intelligence algorithms opens up new possibilities for predicting the course of the disease and individualizing therapy.

Of particular interest are technologies [4]:

- genomics;
- proteomics;
- metabolomics;
- intestinal microbiome analysis.

The use of machine learning systems will allow the creation of personalized predictive models and the optimization of treatment strategies.

Conclusions

Biomarkers are an integral part of modern rheumatology and are important for early diagnosis, assessment of disease activity, prognosis and monitoring of treatment effectiveness. Modern molecular technologies and multi-biomarker systems create the basis for the development of personalized medicine and improved clinical outcomes in patients with rheumatic diseases.

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